

MULTISCALE ANALYSIS ON TOUGHNESS ENHANCEMENT OF EPOXY/SILICA NANOCOMPOSITES WITH INTERFACIAL PARTIAL AND PROGRESSIVE DEBONDING

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ABSTRACT

In this study, multiscale analysis models with particle phase of spherical silica and matrix phase of epoxy are constructed to observe toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites when partial and progressive debonding occurs at interface of the two phases. The interfacial debonding-induced nanovoid growth is known as one of the main toughening mechanisms which caused by internal silica nanoparticles. The mechanism consists of two sub mechanisms – interfacial debonding and subsequent plastic yielding of matrix. Multiscale framework of both toughening mechanisms is constructed with considering interfacial partial and progressive debonding of nanoparticles by applying finite element models. Influences of the specific debonding area and interfacial fracture energy with varying particle volume fraction on the dissipated plastic energy of matrix domain is investigated. As a result, increase of toughness enhancement is observed at increasing specific debonding area, particle volume fraction and interfacial fracture energy. The results provide insights for applying partial and progressive debonding phenomenon in multiscale analysis on the toughness enhancement of nanocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cross-linked epoxy resins are widely used as phase materials of matrix in fiber-reinforced composites. The epoxy composites have merits in material properties like creep resistance and thermal resistance, but they also have inherent brittleness and this weak point results in low fracture toughness of the composites. When a macro crack occurs on the matrix, it propagates very fast in the early part and internal energy of the epoxy system is used in this crack propagation. To relieve the crack propagation and prevent fracture, internal energy of the epoxy system must be dissipated by enhancing

Figure 1. Sub mechanisms of interfacial debonding-induced nanovoid growth mechanism: (a) interfacial debonding [1], (b) plastic yielding of matrix [1] and (c) schema of the toughening sub mechanisms.

fracture toughness of the system. Allegedly, silica nanoparticles are usually added into the epoxy system to make nanocomposites with enhanced Young's modulus, thermal resistance and fracture toughness especially. Hsieh, T. H. *et al.* [2] and Kinloch, A. J. *et al.* [3] observed enhancement of fracture toughness of epoxy composites by adding rubber microparticles, silica nanoparticles and thermoplastic particles. They suggested that energy dissipation of interfacial debonding induced nanovoid growth mechanism which consists of two sub mechanisms – interfacial debonding and subsequent plastic yielding of matrix – is main toughening mechanisms of epoxy composites. An experimental observation of the toughening sub mechanisms are shown in Figure 1 with conceptual schema of both mechanisms. To investigate effects of the toughening mechanisms on toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites, multiscale analysis methodology which can apply energy dissipation following interfacial debonding between particle and matrix is needed.

Zappalorto, M. *et al.* [4] suggested analytical model of toughening mechanisms of epoxy nanocomposites by assuming that matrix and particle are uniformly debonded by each other when the nanocomposites are affected by appropriate critical strain. Toughness enhancements of the nanocomposites induced by the toughening mechanisms can be obtained by the model in a form of energy release rate. However, the constructed model cannot consider interfacial 'partial' debonding phenomena on which S. F. Zheng *et al.* [5] showed importance of the analysis by investigating change of Young's modulus for different partial debonding state. In this study, we constructed multiscale finite element (FE) analysis model that can be employed to calculate fracture toughness of the epoxy/silica nanocomposites in view of energy dissipation with considering interfacial partial and progressive debonding.

Figure 2. Schema of multiscale analysis for interfacial partial and progressive debonding [6].

A schematic view of the objective of this research is shown in Figure 2. When a macro crack tip exists in a silica-epoxy nanocomposites, two-dimensional stress field in macroscale and plane strain condition near the crack tip is considered. A representative volume element (RVE) of finite element (FE) models considering nanoscale interfacial partial and progressive debonding of silica particle phase and epoxy matrix phase are constructed by ABAQUS® (Dassault Systems® Inc.) [7]. Finally, toughness enhancements of the nanocomposites in interfacial partial and progressive debonding cases are predicted by using multiscale analysis model consisting of results from analytic models and FE models.

2 MULTISCALE ANALYSIS MODEL OF PROGRESSIVE AND PARTIAL DEBONDING

The FE models of silica/epoxy nanocomposites considering interfacial partial and progressive debonding are constructed with seven different types of the snapshot structures with hollow-shaped matrix phase and single spherical nanoparticle phase filling the hollow, considering specific debonding areas (ξ) that gradually increase by equivalent amount of area section. The definition of the specific debonding area is as follows:

Figure 3. Example of FE models with 6% particle volume fraction used in the analysis on the interfacial partial and progressive debonding.

$$\xi = \frac{A_{db}}{A_{db}^{\max}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{db}^{\max} is area of the uniform debonding case and A_{db} is area of the partial debonding cases. The progressive process from perfect bonding to uniform debonding of the nanocomposites is represented by the seven snapshot models of the debonding cases. When the specific debonding area is 0, the particle and matrix are in full contact and when the area is 1, they are uniformly debonded. The other five cases with specific debonding area between 0 and 1 are in progressive and partial debonding state. Each model of intermediate step succeeds information about debonding geometry and energy state of the model of the previous step. The examples of the models are shown in Figure 3.

The material properties of each phase and composites are listed in Table 1. The material properties of silica nanoparticle and epoxy matrix are existing results obtained by molecular dynamics simulation [8, 9]. The material properties of composites models are calculated by micromechanics [10] for three cases of particle volume fraction. Radius of each composite model follows radius of corresponding matrix phase.

The multiscale analysis methodology is shown in Figure 4. Analytical model approach [11] is conducted for energy dissipation of interfacial debonding mechanism (U_{db}) and plastic yielding of matrix mechanism ($U_{py}^{analytic}$) at uniform debonding cases by considering interfacial fracture energy (γ_{db}), then the specific debonding area is applied to the results for interfacial debonding mechanism to consider effects of partial debonding as below [12]:

$$U_{db} = U_{db}^{\text{multiscale}} = \gamma_{db} \times 4\pi r_0^2 \times \xi \quad (2)$$

where $U_{db}^{\text{multiscale}}$ is the dissipated energy of the interfacial debonding mechanism obtained from

Elastic properties	Silica	Epoxy	Silica/epoxy nanocomposites		
			Particle volume fraction, %		
			4	5	6
Young's modulus, GPa	104	3.65	3.97	4.05	4.14
Poisson's ratio	0.4054	0.37	0.366	0.365	0.364
Radius, nm	15	-	43.9	40.7	38.3
Yield stress, GPa	-	0.068	-		
Hardening exponent	-	3	-		

Table 1. Elastic properties of silica and epoxy (obtained from MD simulation) and silica/epoxy composite (obtained from Micromechanics)

Figure 4. The multiscale analysis methodology.

multiscale analysis and r_0 is radius of the nanoparticle. The FE model analysis results of energy dissipation of plastic yielding of matrix mechanism (U_{py}^{FEM}) is calculated with considering microscale structure of the interfacial partial debonding by applying specific debonding area on each model. The dissipated energies of the plastic yielding of matrix mechanism obtained by both models are combined to get multiscale result for the mechanism as follows:

$$U_{py} = U_{py}^{multiscale}(\xi) = U_{py}^{analytic} \times \frac{U_{py}^{FEM}(\xi)}{U_{py}^{FEM}(\xi=1)} \quad (3)$$

where $U_{py}^{multiscale}$ is the dissipated energies of the plastic yielding of matrix obtained from multiscale analysis. The dissipated energies are divided by volume of the nanocomposites model (V_{comp}) to get density form (u_{db} , u_{py}) of those of the both toughening mechanisms. Then total toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites can be calculated by conducting J-integral for both dissipated energy densities on stress concentrated region around macro crack tip. The calculated total toughness enhancement of nanocomposites can be expressed as below:

$$\Delta G_{db} + \Delta G_{py} = G_{im} \times \frac{f_p \times (\psi_{db}(u_{db}^{multiscale}) + \psi_{py}(u_{py}^{multiscale}))}{1 - f_p \times (\psi_{db}(u_{db}^{multiscale}) + \psi_{py}(u_{py}^{multiscale}))} \quad (4)$$

where ΔG_{db} is toughness enhancement due to interfacial debonding mechanism, ΔG_{py} is toughness enhancement due to plastic yielding of matrix mechanism, G_{im} is toughness of pure epoxy matrix, f_p is volume fraction of the nanoparticle and ψ_{db} and ψ_{py} are energy dissipation terms of interfacial debonding mechanism and plastic yielding of matrix mechanism, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The multiscale analysis results for four cases of interfacial fracture energies and three cases of particle volume fractions are shown in Figure 5. The interfacial fracture energy values used in the analysis is gradually increased from the smallest value 0.065118 J/m^2 [13] to the largest value 0.1 J/m^2 . The

Figure 5. Toughness enhancement of the multiscale model with initial fracture toughness by specific debonding area for different interfacial energy: (a) 0.065118, (b) 0.07, (c) 0.08 and (d) 0.1 J/m^2 .

toughness of pure epoxy used in the analysis is $283.2 J/m^2$ [14] as an initial point of each graph in the Figure 5. It is confirmed that total toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites increases as specific debonding area and particle volume fraction increase for all graphs in the Figure 5. It is also investigated that when the specific debonding area value is below 0.5, the toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites is less than 30% of the maximum one. On the other hand, when the specific debonding area value is higher than 0.5, the toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites sharply increases and 90% of the maximum toughness enhancement can be obtained for each graph when the specific debonding area reaches to 0.8. The change of the toughness enhancement gradient can be explained by considering relation between specific debonding area and microcrack around each nanoparticle. As the specific debonding area becomes higher than 0.5, shape of microcrack tip around the nanoparticle becomes very sharp and more stress can be concentrated around the microcrack tip. Then more yielding is applied to the matrix around the microcrack tip and this can result in sharp increase of toughness enhancement of the nanocomposites.

4 CONCLUSION

The effects of interfacial partial and progressive debonding on toughness enhancement of silica-epoxy nanocomposites are observed in this research. The results show that toughness of the nanocomposites can be enhanced as specific debonding area and volume fraction of the nanoparticle increase. As there exist some incomplete interfacial debondings with particles and matrix on nanocomposites in real case, the multiscale methodology will be helpful to analyse experimental results and designing material in practical viewpoint. In future work, enhanced methodology will be

developed to observe effects of presence of interphase between particle and matrix as a third phase of nanocomposites on toughness enhancement with interfacial partial and progressive debonding.

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